

Ensemble Approach For The Prediction Of Effect Of Covid-19 Vaccine On Nigerians

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Abstract— This study investigates the effectiveness of ensemble learning techniques in predicting the side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine on Nigerians. A stacking ensemble integrating Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) was employed, with a Random Forest meta-learner. The dataset, sourced from Kaggle, underwent rigorous preprocessing, including handling missing values, encoding categorical features, and balancing using SMOTE. The stacked model achieved superior performance compared to individual models, with a recall of 0.90, F1-score of 0.9474, and ROC-AUC of 0.9875, underscoring the potential of ensemble approaches for improving predictive healthcare analytics.

Keywords—Feature Selection, ensemble learning, Machine Learning, COVID-19, stacking ensemble

I. INTRODUCTION

The global rollout of COVID-19 vaccines has brought hope in controlling the pandemic [1]. However, vaccine hesitancy persists, partly fueled by concerns over side effects[2]–[5]. Several countries have paused or limited the use of the AstraZeneca vaccine due to concerns over rare blood clots in recipients, with Denmark likewise suspending it temporarily as a precautionary measure following reports of blood clots and one death[2], [3], [6].

In Nigeria, the early administration of the COVID-19 vaccine has caused fear among many citizens due to controversial reports and past experiences with other drugs. Many people have expressed various concerns and anxieties about the vaccine [4], [5], [7]. Predicting individual responses to vaccination could play a crucial role in addressing these concerns.

While machine learning (ML) techniques have been widely applied in COVID-19-related predictions such as infection prediction using clinical or imaging data [8], [9], prediction of mortality rate of COVID-19 patients [10], identifications of suitable candidate for COVID 19 vaccination [11], COVID-19 world vaccination progress [12], or on vaccine acceptance [13], limited studies exist on predicting vaccine side effects, particularly among Nigerians.

This study aims to fill this gap by developing an ensemble machine learning model to predict the side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine using a dataset collected from Nigerians. By employing a stacking ensemble approach that integrates

multiple classifiers, the research demonstrates the value of ensemble techniques over individual models, especially in healthcare contexts where minimizing false negatives is critical.

II. RELATED WORKS

The outbreak of COVID-19 in late 2019 led to an urgent global effort to develop vaccines, with various pharmaceutical companies and governments collaborating to curb the virus's spread [14], [15]. Despite successful vaccine rollouts, hesitancy grew due to circulating misinformation and concerns over adverse effects [16]–[23].

Machine learning (ML), particularly supervised learning, has become an essential tool for predictive modeling in healthcare, enabling systems to learn from data and make informed predictions [24], [25]. Common algorithms such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) have been widely used due to their ability to model complex patterns [26], [27].

Ensemble methods, which combine multiple ML models, have shown to improve predictive performance and robustness. These can be homogeneous such as bagging (used in Random Forest) and heterogeneous, as in stacking, which integrates diverse base models using a meta-learner for final predictions [28], [29].

Studies such as [30] have applied ensemble models including Gradient Boosting, RF, and XGBoost to predict COVID-19 cases in Saudi Arabia, showing XGBoost's superior performance. Similarly, [31] predicted global vaccine acceptability using ensemble models like CUBIST and Elastic Net, achieving strong results. [19] Used ML to predict severe vaccine side effects, while [32] employed a voting classifier combining SVM, RF, KNN, and ANN to forecast vaccine-related outcomes from social media data.

In the Nigerian context, few studies exist. [10] Used individual models such as Naïve Bayes and Multilayer Perceptron to predict COVID-19 mortality but did not explore ensemble methods. This highlights a significant research gap, as ensemble approaches are known to outperform single models in terms of generalization and reliability.

Vaccine effectiveness is influenced by various factors. Individual characteristics like age, gender, and immune status

significantly affect immune responses [11], [33], [34]. Vaccine-specific features such as type, dosage, and storage conditions also play a role [35]. Viral mutations like Delta and Omicron have challenged vaccine efficacy, necessitating booster shots [36]. Environmental factors, including climate, air pollution, and population density, further influence vaccine outcomes and model performance [37]–[39]. While ML has proven effective in vaccine-related predictions globally, its application in Nigeria—especially using ensemble models to predict vaccine side effects remains underexplored. Addressing this gap could support more effective public health strategies and localized decision-making.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed Ensemble Approach for the Prediction of effect of Covid-19 Vaccine on Nigerians aims to investigate the effectiveness of ensemble learning techniques in predicting the side effects of the COVID-19 vaccine on Nigerians.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The dataset used was obtained from Kaggle, containing 23 columns capturing demographic data, medical history, and vaccine-related symptoms, totaling 118 instances. Due to its unavailability on Kaggle at the time of this study, a local corpus maintained by the researcher.

Data preprocessing included:

Handling Missing Values: Using mean imputation for numerical features like age, and Simple Imputer for categorical features.

Encoding: Label encoding for the target, one-hot encoding for binary categorical variables, and ordinal encoding for multi-category features.

Class Balancing: Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied to handle class imbalance. Feature selection: Mutual Information was used to retain the most relevant features.

Scaling: Standard Scaler was applied to normalize features.

B. Model Architecture

The proposed model follows a stacked ensemble framework. Four base classifiers; SVM, RF, KNN, and XGB were trained using Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV). Their predictions were combined with the original features and passed to a Random Forest meta-learner. The overall architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Architecture of the proposed ensemble

C. Hyperparameter Tuning

Hyper-parameters for each model were tuned via grid search with cross-validation. Key parameters included:

Table 1. Hyper-parameters explored for SVM model.¹

S/N	Parameter	Value	Meaning/Description
1	Kernel	RBF	Maps inputs into higher dimensions for non-linear separation
2	Gamma	Scale	Controls influence of single training examples
3	Class Weight	Balance	Adjust weight to handle class imbalance

Table 2. Hyper-parameter explored for RF model.²

S/N	Parameter	Value	Meaning/Description
1	Max_depth	3	Limits the maximum depth of each tree to avoid overfitting
2	n_estimators	40	Number of trees in the ensemble
3	Class Weight	Balance	Adjusts class weights to handle imbalance

Table 3. Hyper-parameter explored for RF model.³

S/N	Parameter	Value	Meaning/Description
1	n_neighbors	5	Number of nearest neighbors considered for classification
2	Weights	Distance	Weights closer neighbors more heavily in decision
3	Metrics	Manhattan	Uses Manhattan distance (sum of absolute differences) to measure similarity

Table 4. Hyper-parameter explored for XGB model.⁴

S/N	Parameter	Value	Meaning/Description
1	learning_rate	0.1	Shrinks contribution of each tree, prevents overfitting
2	max_depth	3	Maximum depth of each tree
3	n_estimators	100	Number of boosting rounds (trees)

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Model Performance

Performance metrics; F1-score, Recall (Sensitivity), and ROC-AUC were used to evaluate the models, given the imbalanced dataset. Results are summarized in Table 1.

Model	F1-score	Recall/sensitivity	ROC-AUC
SVM	0.7846	0.7727	0.8348
RF	0.7692	0.7576	0.8133
KNN	0.5385	0.6604	0.8131
XGB	0.6769	0.7040	0.7763
Ensemble	0.9	0.9474	0.9875

The SVM performed best among the base models with a ROC-AUC of 0.8348. RF followed closely, maintaining a good balance of recall and F1-score. Although KNN's recall was lower, its ROC-AUC remained competitive. The XGB model offered balanced but moderate performance.

B. Stacked Ensemble Performance

The stacked ensemble significantly outperformed all base models. It achieved an F1-score of 0.9474, recall of 0.90, and ROC-AUC of 0.9875, indicating excellent ability to identify individuals likely to experience side effects and strong class separability as shown in (Fig. 2) ROC-AUC curve.

Figure 2. The ROC-AUC Curve

This improvement underscores the strength of ensemble learning in aggregating diverse model insights, thereby minimizing false negatives, a critical aspect in healthcare applications.

C. Class Distribution on table

Prior to applying SMOTE, the dataset exhibited clear class imbalance between individuals who reported post-vaccination side effects and those who did not. This imbalance justified the use of SMOTE to synthetically balance the minority class and improve the model learning stability.

Table 5. Class Distribution

Class Label	Description	Original Samples	After SMOTE
0	No side effect	26	67
1	Side effect reported	67	67

The apparent reduction of sample size was not caused by SMOTE but by initial train-test split of the dataset. The original dataset was partitioned into 80% training and 20% testing samples. SMOTE was applied only to the training subset to address class imbalance. The test set was

intentionally left untouched to prevent data leakage and to ensure unbiased performance evaluation.

Figure 3. Number of Side Effects vs No side Effects for Post-SMOTE Distribution

As shown in figure 2, Data preprocessing workflow showing class label before and after applying SMOTE, the training dataset was imbalanced before SMOTE, with 26 samples of class 0 and 67 samples of class 1. After applying SMOTE, both classes were balanced at 67 sample each. This ensures that the classifier does not become biased towards the majority class. The test set was not halted to maintain realistic evaluation conditions.

D. Statistical Testing

To evaluate the reliability and significance of model performance, bootstrap resampling was used to compute 95% confidence intervals for Recall, F1 Score, and ROC AUC. Additionally, McNemar and DeLong tests can be applied to formally assess whether differences in classification accuracy and ROC AUC between the stacked model and base models are statistically significant. These methods provide complementary insights, with McNemar testing label-level differences and DeLong comparing ROC curves based on predicted probabilities

A. Bootstrap confidence interval

Table 6. Statistical Testing

Model	Recall(mean [95% CI])	F1-Score (mean [95% CI])	ROC AUC (mean [95% CI])
SVM	0.787[0.681, 0.881]	0.773 [0.692, 0.849]	0.836 [0.758, 0.909]
RF	0.772[0.667, 0.870]	0.758 [0.673, 0.837]	0.815 [0.730, 0.889]
KNN	0.539[0.414, 0.652]	0.659 [0.549, 0.752]	0.813 [0.735, 0.886]
XGB	0.681[0.569, 0.797]	0.705 [0.605, 0.786]	0.777 [0.686, 0.861]
Stacked	0.899[0.762, 1.000]	0.946 [0.865, 1.000]	0.988 [0.937, 1.000]

The performance of both the base models and the stacked ensemble model was evaluated using Recall, F1 Score, and ROC AUC, with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals to quantify uncertainty. Among the base models, SVM and Random Forest achieved the highest recall, while KNN had the lowest, suggesting it was less sensitive in identifying individuals with vaccine side effects.

The stacked model, which combined all base models using a Random Forest meta-learner, outperformed all individual models across all metrics. Its high recall, F1 score, and ROC AUC, along with narrow confidence intervals, indicate robust and reliable predictive performance. This confirms that ensemble learning effectively leverages the strengths of individual models to improve prediction of COVID-19 vaccine side effects.

B. A McNemar’s test was conducted to compare the predictive performance of the base models and the stacked ensemble. The test produced a contingency table of $[[20, 0], [2, 2]]$ and a p-value of 0.50, indicating that the observed performance difference between the models was not statistically significant ($p \geq 0.05$). This suggests that although the stacked model achieved higher performance metrics, the improvement was not statistically conclusive, possibly due to the small sample size.

C. DeLong Test for ROC comparison

We compared the ROC-AUC of the stacking classifier against the base model with the highest ROC (SVM). The results were:

D. Table 7. DeLong Test for ROC comparison

E.

Model	ROC curve
SVM	0.950
Stacked	0.9875
p-value	0.419

The p-value (0.419) indicates no statistically significant difference between the ROC curves of the stacking classifier and the best-performing base model. This suggests that while the stacking model slightly improves ROC numerically, the improvement is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

V. RECOMMEDATION

Future studies should consider:

1. Using larger and more diverse datasets to enhance generalizability.
2. Exploring advanced ensemble techniques like blending and meta-learning.
3. Conducting real-world pilot tests to validate practical applicability.
4. Employing additional metrics such as precision-recall curves for deeper performance insights.

5. Refining predictions by classifying side effects into mild, severe, or chronic to improve patient management strategies.

The following limitation were identified:

1. The dataset Size is critically small (118 instances), and a more robust dataset is required to reduce the risk of variance inflation, and overfitting.
2. There is risk of overfitting, as the use of LOOCV with stacking ensemble may inflate performance estimate
3. SMOTE generated samples may not fully represent real-world population variability.
4. The model was not validated on an external dataset, which limits its generalizability.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the potential of ensemble learning techniques, specifically stacking, in predicting COVID-19 vaccine side effects on Nigerians. The stacked ensemble model surpassed individual classifiers in all key metrics, offering a more reliable predictive tool. By leveraging diverse algorithms and rigorous preprocessing—including feature selection, missing value handling, and class balancing—the ensemble approach provided superior recall and F1-scores. This highlights its promise for adoption in medical predictive analytics where accurate identification of at-risk individuals is crucial.

VII. DATA ETHICS AND DATA PRIVACY

This study utilized a secondary dataset obtained from Kaggle, an open data-sharing platform, where the dataset was publicly available at the time of access. The dataset did not contain personally identifiable or sensitive personal information. The data were used strictly for academic and research purposes, and no attempt was made to identify or contact any individuals.

To ensure data privacy, all records were handled anonymously, and the dataset was stored securely on a password-protected system accessible only to the researcher. The study adhered to accepted principles of data ethics by maintaining data integrity, avoiding manipulation or misrepresentation of the data, and ensuring that the dataset was used in accordance with appropriate research standards.

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